

THE QURANIC NARRATIVE OF INTERFAITH DIALOGUE: A STUDY OF SYED JALALUDDIN UMARI

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Abstract

Interfaith dialogue in the Qur'an is a subject differently discussed by scholars throughout the world. The Qur'an has asked believers to establish a dialogue with other religions, especially Christianity and Judaism, to come to common terms. Of many other scholars/academicians, Sayed Jalaluddin Umari (1935-2022 CE), a noted Indian scholar and former president (2007-2019 CE) of *Jamat-e-Islami Hind*, has elaborated this idea in his famous work *Tajalliyyaat-e-Qur'an*. The present study will examine the arguments developed in this work to explore the Quranic narrative on interfaith dialogue. He provides some substantial arguments for interfaith dialogue in light of the Qur'an. To him, the dialogue should be initiated on equal terms and apply to each party. Any initiative for interfaith dialogue should be addressed in a free and frank atmosphere wherein the right and wrong ideas should be highlighted peacefully without involving violence. Umari elaborates that such an initiative does not mean any withdrawal from the fundamental teachings of the religion; it rather applies to a mutual understanding of the universal truth as revealed to all the previous Prophets and finally testified by the Qur'an.

Keywords: Ahl al-Kitāb, Cooperation, Dialogue, Qur'an.

INTRODUCTION

The Qur'an, God's final revealed word, is the main normative foundation of Islam, followed by the Sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of God be upon him). The authority and legitimacy of the Qur'an are universally acknowledged by the Muslim community. For Muslims, there is nothing except these two foundational sources that hold the position of undisputable and total authority.

As a result, the Qur'an (and the Sunnah) should be the primary and main source of guidance when seeking an Islamic solution to any issue. Also, it is worth mentioning that amongst the sacred texts of different religions, "the Qur'an is unique in that it sets its worldview within the context of divine oneness and human diversity, including the plurality of religions" (Ayoub 2000: 53-64). Numerous verses, both explicitly and implicitly, talk about the different races, languages, and religions of people.

According to Sohail H. Hashmi, "Hundreds of verses in the Qur'an directly or indirectly refer to the issues of tolerance and intolerance of systems of belief, worship, and conduct other than what it describes as 'the religion that is with God' (al-din 'inda Allah)- al Islam" (Hashmi 2002: 81-103). Such verses unfold the possibilities of "interfaith dialogue" in Islam. Pertinently, the concept of interfaith dialogue or mutual understanding of different religions has been discussed and elaborated by many scholars and academicians in light

of the Qur'an and Sunnah. Among these, Syed Jalaluddin Umari has exhaustively brought this theme under discussion in his book *Tajallīyaat-e-Qur'an*.

Umari was born in 1935 CE in Puttagram village in the North Arcot district of Tamil Nadu, British India. He completed his graduation and Master's in Islamic Studies from Jamia Darussalam, Omarabad, Tamil Nadu. He also received a baccalaureate in English from Aligarh Muslim University. As an Islamic reformer, educationist, researcher, and author, Umari served as the former vice president of the Muslim Personal Law Board and also headed other reputed organizations like *Jamīatul Falah Azamgarh*, and *Tasneefi Academy Delhi*, was the founder and editor of the research journal *Tahqeeqat-e-Islami* (since 1982), and editor of *Zindagi-e-Nau* for half-a-decade. Umari has more than forty books to his credit and a large number of articles on various contemporary aspects of Islam. Some of his best-known works are *Awraaq-e-Seerat*, *Tajallīyaat-e-Qur'an*, *Islam and Service to Mankind*, *Islamic Solution to Human Issues*, *Women, and Islam*. In his prominent works *Tajallīyaat-e-Qur'an*, Umari has exhaustively discussed the concept of interfaith dialogue in Islam, the history of interaction between Muslims and other faiths (people of the book), as well as the history and future prospects of interfaith dialogue.

Interfaith Dialogue from Islamic Perspective

Improving one's awareness of different religions and cultures is essential in today's era of globalization in order to sustain unity amid diversity. The goal of getting to know each other necessitates dialogue among followers of different religions. Therefore, the first duty would be to reflect on the ideological and historical perspectives of different religions in order to uncover and reinforce the virtues of love and mutual respect. The Qur'an has encouraged humanity to help each other in goodness and prohibits anyone from aiding in wrongful acts and oppression. It states:

O you who believe! Do not profane the landmarks of Allah nor any sacred month, nor the offering nor the victims with garlands, nor those repairing to the Sacred House seeking the grace and goodwill of their Lord. And when you have put off the state of sanctity, you may hunt. And let not the detestation for a people, because they kept you from the Sacred Mosque, incite you to trespass. Cooperate with one another in virtue and piety, and do not cooperate in sin and transgression. Fear Allah. Verily Allah is Severe in chastising. (Qur'an 5: 2)

Fazlur Rehman Faridi analyses the significance of the above verse for a diverse society "In a plural society, whoever struggles towards the attainment of equality and justice and removal of human exploitation and denial of human rights, deserves un-reserved cooperation of Muslims" (Faridi 1998: 80).

In contemporary times, dialogue among religions has gained special attention, and it is said that misconceptions and differences among religions should be eradicated to bring them closer to each other. For this purpose, the exchange of ideas, dialogue, and debate is taking place among the followers of different religions, and efforts are being made at various levels to ensure fruitful dialogue. However, Umari argues, that those who strive to put an end to the differences thought that there is no real difference among the religions

and that all religions strive for the satisfaction of the soul and the pleasure of their Lord, every religion considers oppression as a wrongful act, and everyone believes in the significance of justice in human society. In addition, Umari argues, that when we move forward in order to end the differences among different religions, this thing gives rise to a concept called *wahdatul Adīyan* (unity of religions), i.e., every religion has the same goal and the difference is only in the path. In contemporary times, interfaith dialogue is held for such a type of propagation (i.e., propagation of unity of religions). But to Umari, this is a baseless and false concept. The reality is that there is a clear fundamental difference between the religions, which is why all religions cannot be put together (Umari 2013).

Furthermore, Umari states that a dialogue or discussion could be initiated for two purposes: firstly, when an individual is looking for truth and trying to know the reality through discussion or dialogue. Secondly, without discussing the ideas and beliefs, whether they are valid or invalid, a person tries to find common principles on which everyone agrees. Umari avers that Islam does not uphold the second type of dialogue. Islam, as a religion of truth, a complete system of thought and action, seeks to clarify its legitimacy through discussion and debate (Umari 2013).

Unity of the Religions

Sultan Ahmad Islahi argues that the concept of *Wahdatul Adīyan* (unity of religions) is purely Indian philosophy, which especially, is a product of the political conditions of independent India. It may not be wrong to say that it was difficult to build a pluralistic society based on the Hindu religion because of the shortcomings and inabilities of Hinduism (Islahi 2013). Hence, secularism was preferred as a model of government in India. The demand for secularism was to keep religion away from political affairs. For that purpose, the philosophical concept of 'unity of religions' was used by the state (Islahi 2013).

The Islamic standpoint is clear, as Umari avers, that since the inception of Adam and Eve, Islam has been the religion of humanity. Prophets were sent to propagate the same religion at every age or time. However, with the passage of time, their teachings could not remain in their original form and succumbed to distortion. Islam was completed upon the arrival of Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) and the Qur'an, as the last revelation, is preserved in its original form and the criteria of success will be associated with the Qur'an (Umari 2013). The Qur'an has mentioned these things very clearly, "Say: 'O mankind! Verily I am Allah's Messenger to you all'" (Qur'an 7: 158).

Regarding the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) as the seal of Prophethood, the Qur'an declares that "Muhammad is not the father of any of your males, but a Messenger of Allah and the seal of the Prophets, and Allah is the Knower of everything" (Qur'an 33:40).

In addition, it is clearly mentioned in the various verses of the Qur'an that every messenger of God has been given divine commandments and laws according to the need of their time. "And thereafter we have placed upon the law of the religion; so follow it you, and follow not the vain desires of those who do not know" (Qur'an 45:18).

Finally, the Qur'an makes it clear that only the religion of Islam will be accepted by God, and the Qur'an came up with new principles which will be the only way to salvation. "And whoso seeks a religion other than Islam, it shall not be accepted of him and in the Hereafter, he shall be of the lost" (Qur'an 3:85).

While commenting on the above verse, Abdul Majid Daryabadi (d. 1977 CE) states:

This repudiates the comfortable doctrine that all religions are equally good and that different 'paths' adopted by different nations and different grades of society converge to the same Divinity. There is only one straight line possible between any two points. Even so there is only one True, perfect and sound religion. All other religions are but so many deviations (Daryabadi 2001: 128).

Ahl al-Kitāb in the Qur'an

There are differences of opinion among the scholars regarding *ahl al-Kitāb*. Some argue that the phrase "*Ahl al-Kitāb*" refers to Jews, despite the fact that some consider it to denote Christians. However, the third group of scholars holds the view that this term refers to both the Jewish and Christian communities to whom the Qur'an presents an invitation to accept the religion of Islam. For Al-Tabari, while explaining the Quranic verse 3: 64, in the context of this verse, means *ahl al-Tawrat* (the People of the Torah) and *ahl al Injil* (the People of the Gospel) (Wahyudi, 1998). According to Al-Tabari, this verse does not specify either group as Ahl al-Kitāb but includes both ahl al-kitabayn (Wahyudi, 1998). After al-Tabari the major Quranic commentators agreed with his viewpoint. Al-Tusi, for example, offers the same three alternative interpretations of the phrase: People of the Book, namely the Christians of Najran, the Jews of Madinah who worshipped their leaders and their monk, and a combination of both groups (Wahyudi 1998).

Umari avers that the Qur'an uses the term "*Ahl al-Kitab*" for Jews and Christians. To them, God has revealed the *Torah* and *Injeel*. Though these books were distorted, even though the Qur'an calls them *Ahl al-Kitab* as an honor (Umari 2013). According to Ismail Raji al-Faruqi "The respect with which Islam regards Judaism and Christianity, their founders and scriptures, is not a courtesy, but the acknowledgment of religious truth. Islam sees them in the world not as 'other views' which it has to tolerate, but as standing de jure, as truly revealed religions from God. Moreover, their legitimate status is neither socio-political, nor cultural, but religious" (Faruqi 1998; 74).

Umari avers that the Quran has permitted dialogue with the People of the Book, but it should be in the best way:

And dispute not with the people of the Book unless in the best manner, save with those of them who do wrong; and say: we believe in that which hath been sent down unto us and that which hath been sent down unto you: our God and your God is one, and unto Him we are submissive (Qur'an 29:46).

Umari argues that the People of the Book used to believe in the oneness of God, revelation, Prophets, and the hereafter. In this way, they share these basic beliefs with Muslims, though they claim to be monotheistic instead of that the act of association with

God has crept into them. They also claim to believe in the revelation and prophets, but they deny Muhammad's (peace be upon him) prophethood (Umari 2013).

Further, they were asked to believe in the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) and support him, as mentioned in the covenant but they clearly said that would not accept other Prophets.

And when it said to them: 'believe in what Allah has sent down now, they say: 'we believe in what has been sent down to Us'. And they disbelieve in what is besides that while it is the truth, confirming what is with them. Say: 'why then you kill Allah's prophets aforetime if ye have been believers? (Qur'an 2: 91).

Moreover, the Qur'an addresses the people of the book in different ways. As Umari states, like the pagans of Arabia, the people of the book also associate others with God. A Jewish sect called Prophet Uzair the son of God, and Christians used to call Jesus the son of God, but they could not provide any evidence for it (Umari 2013).

And the Jews say, Ezra is a child of God; and the Nazarenes say, the Messiah is a child of God. That is their sayings with their mouths, resembling the saying of those who disbelieved aforetime. Allah confound them! Whither are they turning away (Qur'an 9:30).

In this way, Umari argues People of the Book have similarities with the pagans of Arabia and the Qur'an has clearly associated polytheism with them. Instead of that, they were connected with the concept of Prophethood, revealed books, and the hereafter. Even the pagans of Arabia considered the Jews and Christians as separate from themselves and also regard them as the People of the Book (Umari 2013).

And this is a book we have sent down, blest, follow it then and fear Allah, that you may be shown mercy. Lest you should say: 'The Book was only sent down to the two sects before us, and we were in fact unaware of their readings (Qur'an 6: 155-6).

Both pagans of Arabia and the People of the Book, as Umari states, take their genealogies to Prophet Abraham (peace be upon him), but the Arabia pagans abandoned his teachings. Even Judaism and Christianity came after the Prophet Abraham (peace be upon him) and both were deviated from the way of the Prophet Abraham (peace be upon him) (Umari 2013).

In addition, in some aspects, the history of the People of the Book has been glorious. That was the time of prophethood, religious leadership, and governance. They were the leaders of the world in their time of age and were declared by God as the best nation (Umari, 2013). The Qur'an addresses the Israelites that "O Children of Israel! Remember My favor with which I favored you, that surely I preferred you above the worlds" (Qur'an 2: 47).

Subsequently, the Qur'an has mentioned the qualities of pious people among them and has appreciated them for their virtuous character as well:

Yet were they not all alike. Among the people of the book, there is a community steadfast, reciting the revelation of Allah in the watches of the night while they prostrate themselves. And they believe in Allah and the last day and enjoy good and forbid evil, and vie with

each other in virtues. And these are among the righteous. And whatever of good they do shall not be denied. And Allah is the Knower of the pious (Qur'an 3:113-5).

However, the Qur'an also mentions the dark period of the People of the Book as well, which led them to their downfall.

Stuck upon them is abjection wherever they may be, except in a compact with Allah and in a compact with men; and they have drawn upon themselves wrath from Allah, and struck upon them is poverty. That is because they have been denying the signs of Allah and killing the Prophets of Allah without right. That is because they have disobeyed, and they have been transgressing. (Qur'an 3:112)

So, from the above verse, it is clear that the People of the Book had become disobedient, and yet God reminded them of their actions so that they may take heed and be among the true slaves of their God. Umari argues that the Qur'an has presented before the People of the Book their wrong acts and reminds them that they have become materialistic and heedless about the hereafter. They were reminded of the favors of God, yet they have been ungrateful towards their lord (Umari 2013).

The Common Terms

The Qur'an has invited the People of the Book to come to common terms:

Say: 'O people of the Book! Come to a word common to us and you, that we shall worship none save Allah, and we shall not join anyone with him, and that none of us shall take others as lord besides Allah; then if they turn away; say, bear witness that we are Muslims (Qur'an 3:64).

As Umari states, it is said regarding the above verse that we can call people to common principles without discussing the differences among the religions and everyone should be allowed to act in their own way. This is considered "tolerance" or "broad-mindedness" in the case of religion. However, Umari considered this against the Islamic way of preaching. He argues that the People of the Book were criticized in this verse and they were invited to Islam (Umari 2013). When Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) sent a letter to Heraclius inviting him to accept Islam, he mentioned this verse in the letter (Umari 2013).

In the Quran 3:64, the People of the Book, as Umari avers, were invited to *Kalimatin Sawa'in*. He argues that *Kalimatin Sawa'in* means the oneness of God, which was common between the Muslims and the People of the Book and which was the foundation of all religious books. Though Jews were inclined to believe in God's oneness, there were those among them who called the Prophet Uzayr the son of God in the same way that Christians had adopted the concept of trinity, which was contrary to the concept of Monotheism. In Umari's view, this was actually an invitation (towards Islam) to the People of the Book (Umari 2013).

Umari's interpretation of the phrase "*kalimatin sawa'in*" is not unique; classical scholars have interpreted and understood the phrase in the same way. To substantiate this argument Tabari says, "*kalimatin sawa'in* that is a *kalimatin 'adlin* (a just word), meaning the worship of the one Supreme God without associating others with Him." (Wahyudi,

1998: 427) Moreover, Zamakhshari interprets the phrase “the just word common between us and you as a common word on which the Torah, the Gospel, and the Qur’an would agree. In addition, he interprets the call to worship nothing but God and to associate nothing else with Him, as a call to avoid labeling either Uzayr or Isa as sons of God, because both are simply human beings” (Wahyudi 1998: 428).

In addition, Mustafa Kasim, comments regarding the verse under discussion that “Without doubt, this verse commands the Prophet (PBUH) and therefore the Muslims to establish relations with People of the Book and to unite around common issues. In a way, it draws a framework for dialogue. Common issues around which we can come together may be principles of faith such as faith in God, prophets and the afterlife, principles of practice such as abstinence from adultery, gambling or drinking, or temporal political, social, cultural or economic issues” (Kuruca and Erol 2012:34-35). Moreover, Akhtarul Wasey, comments regarding this verse (3:64) that “here the addresses are the people of the Book present at that time. This verse could be assumed to have addressed the people of other religions as well, offering to come together to take on common terms” (Wasey 2008: 121).

However, Umari contends that the differences cannot be resolved because Muslims and People of the Book differ in fundamental religious beliefs, and efforts to eliminate these differences would be futile. Although, efforts could be made together regarding our common issues and problems which include social and ethical issues (Umari 2013). To substantiate this argument, Sevket Yavuz and Davut Ayduz state that “it is not Islamic conduct and ethics to cut off our relations with the People of the Book, or behave harshly, or look down on them. This mode of conduct and praxis apparently contradicts the main character of Islam in general and of the Qur'an in particular. In another way, the Qur'an reinstates this rule in this way: Allah forbids you not, with regard to those who fight you not for (your) Faith nor drive You out of your homes, from dealing kindly and justly with them: for Allah loveth those who are just” (Yavuz and Aydüz 2007: 97).

CONCLUSION

The Qur’an provides a beautiful narrative of interfaith dialogue, especially with Christians and Jews. According to the Qur’anic dictates, the dialogue must be initiated sincerely in an academic atmosphere in order to trace out the common teachings of all the revealed religions. The Qur’an advocates the ideology of unity of religion, emphasizing the similarity of the essence of the religions as maintained by all the scriptures, having different and varying laws according to the needs of the time. Dialogue should be conducted wisely in a friendly atmosphere to search for common grounds for welfare activities and developmental programs universally recognized by all religions. Thus, the Qur’an acknowledges religious pluralism and instructs its followers to respect other religions. The basic principle of interreligious conservation is to eradicate misconceptions and recognize differences. The goal is to create an atmosphere of peaceful coexistence, which is much required in today’s era.

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